

On the Sum of two Polygonal Numbers and Conditions for Closure

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Abstract

Polygonal numbers arise from geometrical patterns of dots or points forming regular polygons and include known sequences such as triangular and square numbers. A natural question in number theory is whether the sum of two polygonal numbers of same order itself is a polygonal number of that order. This paper studies the equation

$$P_n(a) + P_n(b) = P_n(c)$$

where $P_n(k)$ denotes the k -th n -gonal polygon. Using a combination of experimental observation, computational evidence, and theoretical analysis, we examine this equation for different values of n . We show that triangular and square numbers are not closed under addition, yet give infinitely many solutions, with square case precisely corresponding with pythagorean identity. By contrast, higher polygonal numbers ($n \geq 5$) show rapid decline in additive structure, with solution becoming extremely rare. Computational evidence support this result and explains why the solutions disappear as n increases

1. Introduction

Polygonal numbers arise from geometric arrangements of points forming regular polygons. Polygonal numbers have been studied extensively in classical number theory [4, 1]. Among these, triangular and square numbers are particularly well known and exhibit elegant algebraic properties. A natural question in number theory is whether the sum of two polygonal numbers of the same type is again a polygonal number of that type.

While this question has simple answers in special cases, a general understanding remains limited.

This paper examines the equation

$$P_n(a) + P_n(b) = P_n(c),$$

Where $P_n(k)$ denotes the k -th polygonal number of order n . We analyze this equation for various values of n , identify infinite families of solutions where it exists, and demonstrate why such families disappear for higher polygonal families.

2. Preliminaries

2.1 Polygonal numbers

In mathematics, a polygonal number is a number that counts dots arranged in the shape of a regular polygon. These are one type of 2-dimensional figurate numbers. The k -th n -gonal number is defined by the following relation

$$P_n(k) = \frac{(n-2)k^2 - (n-4)k}{2}, \quad n \geq 3, k \geq 1.$$

Special cases include:

- a) Triangular numbers: $T_k = P_3(k) = \frac{k(k+1)}{2}$
- b) Square numbers: $S_k = P_4(k) = k^2$
- c) Pentagonal numbers: $P_5(k) = \frac{3k^2 - k}{2}$
- d) Hexagonal numbers: $P_6(k) = 2k^2 - k$
- e) Heptagonal numbers: $P_7(k) = \frac{5k^2 - 3k}{2}$

3. Experimental Exploration

Before attempting actual proof, an experimental observation was conducted to identify patterns in the sum of polygonal numbers and to determine if the sum results in polygonal numbers of the same order. This approach follows the philosophy of experimental mathematics, where computation guides conjecture formation.

3.1 Computational setup

The n -gonal number is defined as

$$P_n(k) = \frac{(n-2)k^2 - (n-4)k}{2}, \quad n \geq 3, k \geq 1.$$

For fixed value of k , small integers $a, b \leq 30$ were examined and sum of the form

$$P_n(a) + P_n(b)$$

were computed. These sums were checked against known polygonal numbers to determine whether they could be expressed in the form

$$P_n(c) \quad \text{for some integer } c$$

3.2 Case Study: Triangular numbers

Triangular numbers are given by

$$T_n = \frac{n(n+1)}{2}$$

A table of values was conducted for small n :

a	b	$T_n(a) + T_n(b)$	Polygonal?
1	2	4	Not Triangular
2	2	6	T_3
3	4	16	Not Triangular
4	5	25	Not Triangular
5	6	36	T_8

Observation:

The sum of two triangular numbers is not always triangular. Closure under addition does not hold in general. However, several cases of the form $T_a + T_b = T_c$ were observed, suggesting special solutions exist.

3.3 Case Study: Square numbers

Square numbers are given by

$$S_n = n^2$$

Similar table was constructed for smaller values of n .

a	b	$S_a + S_b$	Polygonal?
1	2	5	Not Square
2	3	10	Not Square
3	4	25	S_5
4	10	116	Not Square
5	12	169	S_{13}

Observation:

For squares, $S_a + S_b = S_c$ exist only for Pythagorean triples. Since they are infinite in number, so square numbers are “sometimes close” under specific addition.

3.4 Case Study: Pentagonal numbers

Pentagonal numbers are given by,

$$P_5(k) = \frac{3k^2 - k}{2}$$

Similarly, table is given below for smaller values of n

a	b	$P_a + P_b$	Polygonal?
1	2	6	Not Pentagonal
2	3	17	Not Pentagonal
3	4	34	Not Pentagonal
4	5	57	Not Pentagonal
5	5	70	P_7

Observation:

Unlike triangular and square numbers, sum of pentagonal numbers rarely produces another pentagonal number as seen above. No consistent pattern emerged, implying that closure doesn't hold true and only admits non-trivial solutions.

4. Conjectures

Based on our experimental observation in **section 3** for triangular, square and pentagonal, we propose the following conjectures for those numbers

4.1 Triangular Numbers:

The set of triangular numbers is not closed under addition. Nevertheless, the equation $T_a + T_b = T_c$ admits infinitely many solutions in positive integers.

4.2 Square Numbers:

There are infinitely many solutions to the $S_a + S_b = S_c$ for square numbers if and only if (a, b, c) forms a Pythagorean triple. All the observed solution in **section 3** is in accordance with this conjecture.

4.3 Pentagonal Numbers:

For pentagonal numbers, although there might be several solutions to the equation $P_a + P_b = P_c$, but it admits at most finitely non-trivial solutions.

5. Proofs & Theoretical Analysis

5.1 Triangular Numbers:

Proposition 1:

Triangular numbers are not closed under addition, but there exist infinitely many solutions to

$$T_a + T_b = T_c$$

Proof:

Using the formula for triangular numbers, we have

$$\frac{a(a+1)}{2} + \frac{b(b+1)}{2} = \frac{c(c+1)}{2}$$

Solving we get,

$$a^2 + a + b^2 + b = c^2 + c$$

Putting $a = b$,

$$c^2 + c - 2a^2 - 2a = 0$$

or,

$$c^2 + c - 2a(a+1) = 0 \text{ ————— (i)}$$

Eqn (i) is quadratic in c , so it has solutions whenever its discriminant i.e $1 + 8a(a+1)$

is a perfect square. Such result gives yield to infinitely many solutions as values will occur infinitely in the given discriminant. Hence, there are infinitely many solutions to the triangular numbers, but aren't closed under addition.

5.2 Square Numbers:

Proposition 2 :

The equation $S_a + S_b = S_c$ holds if and only if (a, b, c) is a Pythagorean triple.

Proof:

This follows directly from classical characterization of integers solution to the Pythagorean equation. Hence, the equation only holds true for Pythagorean triple.[2].

5.3 Higher Polygonal numbers:

Proposition 3 :

For polygonal numbers of order $n \geq 5$, the equation

$$P_n(a) + P_n(b) = P_n(c)$$

doesn't admit infinitely many non-trivial solutions in positive integers

Proof:

The general formula for k -th n -gonal numbers is

$$P_n(k) = \frac{(n-2)k^2 - (n-4)k}{2}, \quad n \geq 3, k \geq 1.$$

Substituting this into the equation

$$P_n(a) + P_n(b) = P_n(c)$$

And Simplifying we get,

$$(n - 2) (a^2 + b^2 - c^2) = (n - 4) (a + b - c) \quad \text{————— (i)}$$

For $n \geq 5$, (i) both coefficients' $(n - 2)$ and $(n - 4)$ are positive

The left hand is quadratic in a, b, c while the right hand is linear. For the larger values of a, b, c , the quadratic terms dominate the linear term forcing

$$a^2 + b^2 \approx c^2$$

Thus, any sufficiently large solutions must be a Pythagorean estimate. However, Unlike the square case ($n = 4$), the presence of non-zero terms in the (i) prevents the equation from reducing exactly to the Pythagorean equation. Therefore, any solution to (i) must satisfy the both the quadratic approximation as well as the linear term. This in turn significantly reduces the number of solution of (i). The computational verification for small values of a, b (upto 30) confirms this result and no recurring patterns emerged. As n increases, the solution becomes rarer and rare. Hence, for $n \geq 5$, the equation admits at most finitely many non-trivial solutions.

6. Higher Polygonal Numbers

6.1 Pentagonal Numbers

Pentagonal numbers are defined by

$$P_5(k) = \frac{3k^2 - k}{2}$$

Our experimental Table in 3.4 showed that sum of pentagonal numbers rarely equals another pentagonal number. However, non-trivial solutions do exist to the equation. For example,

$$P_5(5) + P_5(5) = 35 + 35 = 70 = P_5(7)$$

Algebraically, the closure equation reduces to

$$3(a^2 + b^2 - c^2) = a + b - c,$$

a quadratic equation with linear term. Unlike the square case, this equation doesn't reduce to standard equation, which helps explain why the number of solutions decreases.

6.2 Hexagonal Numbers

Hexagonal numbers satisfied

$$P_6(k) = 2k^2 - k = k(2k - 1),$$

and forms a sequence of triangular numbers by simple analysis. This relation might suggest that hexagonal numbers likely inherited structure from triangular numbers of any additive patterns, but sparsity of subsequence made the closure under addition unlikely.

6.3 Heptagonal Numbers

Heptagonal numbers are given by

$$P_7(k) = \frac{5k^2 - 3k}{2}$$

As n increased, polygonal sequences became sparser and the closure equation imposed stronger arithmetic constraints. This suggested a decreasing frequency of solutions within bounded search ranges.

6.4 Computational Evidence

A brute-force search over $1 \leq a \leq b \leq 500$ was conducted for $n = 3, 4, 5, 6, 7$. Let N_n denote the number of pairs ab producing a solution c within the same bound. The total number of tested pairs was $\frac{500 \cdot 501}{2} = 125,250$.

Order n	N_n solutions (within bound)	Hit rate
3 (triangular)	737	0.588%
4 (square)	386	0.308%
5 (pentagonal)	182	0.145%
6 (hexagonal)	164	0.131%
7 (heptagonal)	97	0.077%

This quantified the observed decline in solution density as n increased.[3].

7. Discussion

7.1 Why Closure Disappears

Two effects appeared to be reason for the loss of closure. First, higher polygonal families are sparser, so random sums are less likely to land exactly on the same sequence. Second, the closure equation

$$(n - 2)(a^2 + b^2 - c^2) = (n - 4)(a + b - c)$$

combines quadratic constraints with a linear correction term. For squares ($n = 4$) the linear term vanished and the equation became exactly Pythagorean, producing infinitely many well-understood solutions, but for $n \geq 5$, the correction term restricted solutions more strongly, and the computations suggested that solutions persisted but became increasingly rare.

7.2 Limitations

This work did not classify all integer solutions for each n , and computational results were necessarily bounded. Absence of patterns within a finite range did not constitute non-existence, but it did provide evidence about relative frequency. The theoretical analysis was therefore strongest for the square case, partial for the triangular case, and primarily heuristic for higher orders.

8. Conclusion and Future Work

We studied when the sum of two polygonal numbers of the same order remained polygonal of that order. Triangular and square numbers were not closed under addition, yet both admitted infinitely many solutions, with the square case fully characterized by Pythagorean triples. For higher orders, solutions continued to exist but appeared increasingly sparse within bounded searches. Future work includes extending searches to larger bounds, investigating mixed-type equations $P_n(a) + P_m(b) = P_t(c)$, and applying deeper tools (e.g., Pell-type methods and related Diophantine techniques) to classify or parametrize solution families for $n \geq 5$.

References

- [1] Leonard Eugene Dickson. *History of the Theory of Numbers, Vol. II: Diophantine Analysis*. Chelsea Publishing Company, 1952.
- [2] Ivan Niven, Herbert S. Zuckerman, and Hugh L. Montgomery. *An Introduction to the Theory of Numbers*. Wiley, 5 edition, 1991.
- [3] OEIS Foundation Inc. The on-line encyclopedia of integer sequences. <https://oeis.org>. Accessed January 2026.
- [4] Eric W. Weisstein. Polygonal number. MathWorld—A Wolfram Web Resource. Accessed January 2026.

Appendix (Python codes)

—computational evidence—

```
def polygonal(n, k):
    return ((n - 2) * k * k - (n - 4) * k) // 2
def find_hits(n, MAX=500):
    vals = [polygonal(n, k) for k in range(1, MAX + 1)]
    idx = {v: i + 1 for i, v in enumerate(vals)} # value -> index (c)
    hits = []
    for a in range(1, MAX + 1):
        va = vals[a - 1]
        for b in range(a, MAX + 1):
            s = va + vals[b - 1]
            if s in idx:
                hits.append((a, b, idx[s]))
    return hits

MAX = 500
total_pairs = MAX * (MAX + 1) // 2

for n in [3, 4, 5, 6, 7]:
```

```
hits = find_hits(n, MAX=MAX)
print(n, len(hits), "hit_rate=", len(hits) / total_pairs)
```